

Thiopegan Derivatives. Part XXIV. Syntheses of 9,10-Thiopega-10-en-4-one and 10,11-Thiopega-9-en-4-one

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Condensation product of 2-ethoxycarbonylphénylthiourea and ethylene dibromide has been assigned the angular structure, 9,10-thiopega-10-en-4-one, through its synthesis by the ring closure of 1-(β -hydroxyethyl)-2-mercapto-tetrahydroquinazol-4-one. Ring closure of 2-(β -hydroxyethyl)thio-4-ketotetrahydroquinazoline could not be accomplished. The linear isomer, 10, 11-thiopega-9-en-4-one, has been synthesised by various routes, starting from 2-amino-(β -hydroxyethyl)benzamide.

Condensation of the compounds (I) and (II) furnished only one product¹ though formation of two products (III and IV) was possible. It was considered therefore essential to effect unambiguous syntheses of compounds (III) and (IV).

Earlier attempts² of the synthesis of (III) on the following lines did not materialise because of the failure of effecting ring closure of (V).

1. Khosla *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1953, 12B, 466.

2. Narang *et al.*, *Res. Bull. Panjab Univ.*, 1956, No.87, p. 49.

It has now been possible, however, to effect the ring closure of compound (V) by prolonged heating in acetic acid, saturated with dry hydrochloric acid, the product being identical with the one obtained by condensation of (I) and (II); the probable course of the reaction in the latter case being :

Attempts at the ring closure of (VII), obtained by condensation of compound (VI) with ethylene chlorohydrin to provide (III) or (IV), did not succeed as:

Synthesis of the linear thiopegan (IV) has been achieved by the following routes:

The reactions of (X) with potassium sulphocyanide could proceed in two ways:

Attempted single-step synthesis of (IV) by heating (VIII) with ammonium thiocyanate furnished 2-mercaptotetrahydroquinazol-4-one (VI), presumably by the splitting of the ethanolamine from the intermediate (XII) as:

EXPERIMENTAL

9,10-Thiopega-10-en-4-one (III).—Dry HCl gas was passed through a boiling solution of compound (V) (2.2 g.) in acetic acid for 21 hours. The solvent was removed under vacuum and the residue (1.9 g.) was basified with a cold NaOH solution in which a major portion dissolved. From the alkaline solution the product was precipitated with acetic acid and crystallised from the latter. It was found identical with compound (V). The residue from above on crystallisation from ethanol furnished white needles, m.p. 240°; it was found identical with compound (III)' (undepressed mixed m.p.), yield being 0.3 g. (15%).

2-(β -Hydroxyethyl)thio-4-ketotetrahydroquinazoline (VII).—Ethylene chlorhydrin (0.8 g., 1M) was added with shaking to a solution of 2-thio-4-keto-3,4-dihydroquinazoline

*Melting points are uncorrected. Analyses are by Drs. Weller and Straus, Oxford.

(1.87 g., 1.0M) in a 2% NaOH (0.4 g., 1.0M) solution (20 ml). After keeping overnight, the white solid was collected and crystallised from dilute ethanol in white, flat, rectangular plates, m.p. 95°, yield 1.0 g. (50%). (Found: N, 12.22. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 12.61%.)

Attempted Ring closure of (VII).—(a). Dry HCl gas was passed through a boiling solution of (VII) (2.2 g.) in ethanol for 5 to 6 hours. The white solid separating was collected and crystallised from acetic acid. It was found identical with (VI) through its m.p. and mixed m.p. The filtrate after removal of the solvent deposited compound (VII) unchanged.

Similarly by repeating the experiment in acetic acid solution instead of ethanol, only the original product was obtained.

(b). To powdered dry compound (VII) (2 g.) was added an excess of thionyl chloride (20 ml) and the mixture was kept for an hour. After removal of the latter under vacuum, the black sticky mass could not be purified.

10,11-*Thiopega-9-en-4-one* (IV)

2-Thio-3-(β-hydroxyethyl)-4-ketotetrahydroquinazoline (IX).—A solution of NaOH (0.4 g., 1.0M) in ethanol (20 ml) was added to a solution of 2-amino-(β-hydroxyethyl)-benzamide (VIII)³ in the same solvent (20 ml). Carbon bisulphide (0.76 g., 1.0 M) was added to the above in the cold, followed by refluxing. After half an hour a light yellow solid began to separate in increasing amount with time. Heating was stopped after 2 hours when practically whole of carbon disulphide had been consumed. It was cooled, the solid (Na-salt) was collected under suction, dissolved in water, and precipitated with acetic acid. The precipitate was collected under suction and crystallised from ethanol or acetic acid as shining, white needles, m.p. 240°, yield 0.9 g. The ethanolic filtrate after removal of the solvent and working up in the same fashion afforded the same compound (0.35 g.). (Found: N, 12.74; S, 14.4. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 12.61; S, 14.41%.)

10,11-Thiopega-9-en-4-one: Ring-closure of (IX).—(a). Dry HCl gas was passed through a boiling solution of compound (IX) (2.2 g.) in ethanol (30 ml) for 2 hours, when a white solid separated. The solvent was removed and the residue after basification with sodium carbonate was collected and washed with NaOH solution to remove the unchanged compound (IX). On crystallisation from ethanol, it furnished white needles, m.p. 154°, yield 1.1 g. (55%).

(b). Compound (IX) (1.1 g.) was dissolved in fuming HCl (10 ml) by heating on a water bath for about 15 minutes. It was basified with NaOH in the cold; the solid, thus obtained, on crystallisation from ethanol did not depress the m.p. on admixture with the compound obtained above, yield being 0.6 g. (60%).

o-Amino-(β-chloroethyl)benzamide Hydrochloride (X).—Thionyl chloride (1.2 g.) was added to the dry compound (VIII) (powdered, 1.8 g.) during 15 minutes. A vigorous reaction took place. The yellow sticky product was dissolved in ethanol and precipitated with ether. On crystallisation from dioxane, it furnished white, shining needles, m.p. 148°, yield 2.0 g. (83%). (Found: N, 11.45. $C_9H_{11}ON_2Cl_2$ requires N, 11.95%.)

10,11-*Thiopega-9-en-4-one* from (X).—(a). Well powdered potassium sulphocyanide (2.0 g., 2*M*) was added to a solution of the preceding compound (X) (2.35 g., 1*M*) in ethanol (40 ml) and kept overnight. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue washed thoroughly with water. It weighed 2.0 g. and melted with a range at 270-90°. Attempts at crystallisation of this compound furnished in the end the compound melting at 154° which also did not depress the m.p. on admixture with samples obtained in previous experiments, yield being 0.2 g. (10%).

(b). Dry HCl gas was passed through a boiling solution of the crude product (XI) in ethanol. A yellow solid separating was filtered and the solvent from the filtrate removed. The residue after basification and crystallisation from ethanol was found to be identical with the compound obtained above.

(c). A solution of *o*-amino-(β -chloroethyl)benzamide hydrochloride (X) (2.35 g.) in ethanol was refluxed with potassium sulphocyanide (2.0 g., 2*M*) for 8 hours. A yellow solid separated which was filtered. The solvent from the filtrate was removed and the residue on basification and crystallisation from ethanol furnished the product melting at 154°; yield 0.4 g. (20%). (Found: C, 58.98; H, 4.07; N, 13.65; S, 16.30. $C_{10}H_9ON_2S$ requires C, 58.84; H, 3.92; N, 13.73; S, 15.69%).

The yellow mass obtained during the passage of HCl gas in (a) and during heating in (b) and (c) could not be purified.

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